

Conflict of Interest

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This note provides guidance on identifying and managing conflicts of interest within activities supported by the ESMO International Project Office.

Members of the governing panels of ESMO; the ESMO SSG and other WCRP activities supported by the ESMO IPO must pay attention to issues of independence and bias in order to maintain the integrity of, and community confidence in the standards, guidance and processes resulting from their activities. It is essential that the work of these entities is not compromised by any conflict of interest arising from members' other activities and affiliations.

Overview

The following procedure is designed to ensure conflicts of interest are identified, communicated to the relevant parties, and managed to avoid any adverse impact on decision making, products and processes, thereby protecting the individual, the ESMO governing bodies, WCRP and the wider community's interests.

The individual member and those members of any ESMO IPO supported activity/ESMO governing body should not be placed in a situation that could lead a reasonable person to question, and perhaps discount or dismiss, the work of the group/body simply because of the existence of a conflict of interest. Identifying a potential conflict of interest does not automatically mean that a conflict of interest exists – the purpose of the procedures set out is to enable individuals to provide the relevant information necessary for each particular situation to be evaluated.

Compliance with the Conflict of Interest Implementation Procedures set out below is encouraged for any ESMO IPO supported activities. All interests that could be considered a conflict of interest should be declared by members: <https://shorturl.fm/FzaTZ>. If you are registering a conflict of interest related to a CMIP subsidiary body (CMIP Task Teams or Working Groups), please use this form: <https://bit.ly/ESMO-CMIP-subsiadiary-Col-form>. The Log of interests is made available by the IPO for inspection at each ESMO IPO supported activity meeting, or on request by any member of the WCRP secretariat, WCRP JSC, ESMO IPO or ESMO SSG.

Unless an exception is agreed, an individual cannot participate in a ESMO IPO facilitated activity/ESMO governing body's work where that individual has not complied with the procedures. Where a conflict of interest is identified, a person may only proceed to participate in the activity/ESMO governing body's activities if action is undertaken that resolves the conflict.

Conflict of interest

Definition

1. We adopt the definition as set out in the IPCC Conflict of Interest Policy clause 11:

A “conflict of interest” refers to any current professional, financial or other interest which could:

1. significantly impair the individual’s objectivity in carrying out his or her duties and responsibilities for the ESMO IPO supported activity or
2. create an unfair advantage for any person or organization.

For the purposes of this policy, circumstances that could lead a reasonable person to question an individual’s objectivity, or whether an unfair advantage has been created, constitute a potential conflict of interest. These potential conflicts are subject to disclosure.

2. Disclosure is distinct from ‘bias’ – for instance, holding a view that one believes to be correct, but that one, or one’s affiliations, does not stand to gain from personally, is not a conflict of interest.
3. Significant and relevant interests may include, but are not limited to, another panel or working group they are a member of; senior editorial roles; advisory committees associated with private sector organizations; memberships on boards of non-profit or advocacy groups; employment relationships; consulting relationships; financial investments; intellectual property interests; and commercial interests and sources of private-sector research support. However, not all such associations necessarily constitute a conflict of interest. Care should be taken to recognise where conflicts might be perceived, even if the member feels confident it won’t affect their decision. If a situation could be perceived as a conflict of interest, it’s best to treat it as one.

Exclusions

4. For the avoidance of doubt, disclosure does not apply to past interests that have expired, no longer exist, and cannot reasonably affect current behaviour, nor does it apply to possible interests that may arise in the future but that do not currently exist, as such interests are inherently speculative and uncertain.

Conflict of Interest Implementation

Raising a conflict

5. As soon as a member becomes aware of a conflict, actual or perceived, it should be raised with the appropriate ESMO IPO supported activity Co-Chairs/Co-leads and the WCRP IPO responsible for maintaining the Register of Interests. If a possible conflict involves both Co-Chairs/Co-leads, this should be raised with the ESMO IPO supported activity members and the IPO.
6. Some interests may not present a conflict straight away, but activity members should still declare their key interests regularly.
 - a) For long term interests, such as joining a new organisation as an employee or director, the interest should be declared and included in the Register of interests, maintained by the IPO.
 - b) For a short-term interest or a conflict of interest, the member should declare that interest at the start of any meeting, before any decisions are taken or discussion relating to the area of conflict.
7. When an ESMO IPO supported activity member declares a conflict of interest, the Co-Chairs/Co-leads of that activity should agree on how to manage this, in line with these conflict-of-interest procedures. If a conflict of interest involves both Co-Chairs/Co-leads, the activity members should collectively agree on how to manage this, in line with these conflict-of-interest procedures.

Managing a conflict of interest

8. **If the conflict is low risk**, and the activity member is able to meaningfully contribute, the Co-Chairs/Co-leads or the activity members (in event that that the interest is declared by both Co-chairs) may choose to note the interest of that Member formally in the meeting note/minutes, but allow them to participate in the discussion. The Member may be excluded from any voting that takes place.
9. **If the conflict is high risk**, and the Member is unable to participate without being influenced (or if it might be seen that way by an outside observer), the Co-Chairs/Co-leads or the activity members (in event that that the interest is declared by both Co-chairs) should ask the Member either to not participate in, or, to remove their presence from, the relevant discussion.
10. **If a conflict regularly** prevents a member from participating in decision-making, the Co-Chairs/Co-leads or the activity members (in event that that the interest is declared by both Co-chairs) should consider reviewing that Member's position and making sure they're still able to carry out their role. If they're not able to fully contribute, they may be asked to step down.